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Legal Culture as the Main Factor of Establishing a Legal Democratic State

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***Abstract:** This article provides information on the fact that the development of legal culture at a high level is an important tool for building a legal democratic state, and therefore, legal culture is one of the main criteria for the development of society and one of the important factors of people's way of life.*

***Key words:** Law, culture, legal consciousness, society, group, person, civil society, democracy, law, social, economic, reform, politics, personal interest, community interest, idea, legal education, family, state bodies, legal democratic state, law creation, development prospects, law, decision.*

In the process of today's globalization, achieving the improvement of legal culture, literally raising the legal consciousness, has become the demand of the time. One of the important conditions for building a legal democratic state is the improvement of legal culture. As long as citizens do not develop a high level of legal thinking, various imbalances will arise. Forming a legal culture and thereby achieving the rule of law is valuable not only for the society, but also for the growing youth. The only condition for building a legal state and civil society is unconditional obedience to laws. Large-scale reforms are being implemented in the republic to establish a legal democratic state and civil society. One of the most important signs of the rule of law - ensuring the rule of law and raising a mature generation with a high level of legal awareness and culture is the core of these reforms. It is very important to raise legal awareness and legal culture in the society, to inculcate the spirit of respect for laws in the minds of the country's population and youth. In order for a person to consider himself legally mature and educated, he must first of all develop a spirit of respect for the legal norms established in society. The legal basis of the reforms carried out over the past years has been created. The legal foundations of socio-political life were consistently strengthened. In solving issues of human rights and their protection, it is important for states to adhere to legal norms, and for the legal documents developed in them to be effective and fair. Also, legal propaganda is an educational and promotional method aimed at conveying the legal policy and strategic goals of society and the state to citizens and the public. The

formation of legal culture also depends on the effectiveness of legal propaganda and its comprehensibility to the people.

In the process of building a democratic state, strengthening legislation and ensuring social justice are considered important conditions. Legal culture, which is an integral part of culture, directly and indirectly affects the formation of consciousness and activity in various spheres of people's lives. Our great scientists have expressed their opinions on the concept of legal culture. For example, in his famous work "The City of Virtuous People", Farabi emphasized the concept of legal culture, that is, in the sense that the supremacy of the law, which is the most important factor in the implementation of human rights and freedoms, should be observed in a virtuous city, he stated the following recites: "it is necessary for the city to know the laws, regulations and customs introduced by the first imams, to remember them and to follow them in their actions" [1]. Conducts research on the formation and gives his definitions to the concept of legal culture.

According to E. Kadirov, "Legal culture is a component of social culture, it is a person's assimilation of national and international legal norms at the level of contemporary requirements under the influence of social, legal and political institutes, on the basis of national mentality, legal and political socialization, self It is the practical sum of individual legal consciousness, legal knowledge and legal behavior about one's rights and duties" [2]. In fact, in the process of increasing the legal culture of a person, he should have mastered all the norms recognized by the law at the level of the requirements of the time and should follow them.

Kh.T. Odilkariyev "Legal culture means the educational level of the legal system established in the society, the state of awareness of the people about this legal system, the respect of citizens for the law, the implementation of legal norms, the level of tolerance for those who do not follow the law, and the level of obedience to the law" [3]. Based on this, it can be said that a person with legal culture is aware of the legal system of his country and should be obedient to the current laws.

Sh.A. Saidullayev said, "Legal culture is the level of legal knowledge of people, their conscious attitude towards law, respect for law and compliance with it. Legal culture is an integral part of the general culture of society. Therefore, legal culture means the legal life of the society, its legal reality, normative and legal documents, the spiritual-ethical and legal value system that represents the level achieved in the development of legal consciousness, as well as obedience to the law that makes decisions in accordance with it, and the legal and order environment in the country. "It is understood the implementation of the regulation of social relations for establishment" [4] gives a broad definition of the concept of legal culture.

Scientists of our country, A. Saidov and U. Tadzhikhanov, refer to legal culture as "a form of social culture, which reflects the understanding of legal norms and the practical expression of actions related to their implementation. Legal culture is a form of the general culture of a person, which is expressed in knowledge of all legal norms, strict adherence to them and successful implementation in life, respect for the rights and freedoms of other citizens, and intolerant behavior towards offenders" [5] rates as. Therefore, in order to have a legal culture, it is necessary to have a scientific understanding of the legal foundations and existing legal norms in the society, as well as to be closely familiar with the system of moral values.

At the same time, V.Salnikov, conducting his scientific research on legal culture, considers legal culture as a social phenomenon and defines it as follows: "legal culture is the most important part of legal reality in practical activities in the direction of the consistent development of society and the individual. a unique social phenomenon that covers the whole of its important elements" [6].

In almost all of his speeches, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan focuses on the importance of legal culture and the issues of improving it more than ever. For example, in his speech dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the first Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (December 7, 2016), he says: "In order to ensure the rule of law, it is important to raise legal culture and educate citizens in the spirit of respect for the law" [7]. Therefore, the legal culture of the individual and the society is an important result of universal human value concepts and human democratic achievements.

Summary. Legal culture is an integral part of the legal state. Just as there are means of providing each element, legal culture does not lack means of providing. The means of ensuring legal culture include the current legislation, as well as the level of awareness of the legal system; to have legal knowledge and legal awareness; including compliance with all legal norms and intolerant attitude towards those who do not comply with the law. Most of the problems of society's development are related to the need to improve the legal culture in general. After completing professional education, young professionals should, on the one hand, be psychologically and practically ready for the changes taking place in society, and on the other hand, increase the independence of behavior within the framework of social responsibility and moral and legal norms. . It can be concluded that today's Uzbek youth must have a level of legal culture that can meet the requirements of the time.

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